

Deliverable 6.4.5: Showcase of extended target data and analysis

For paper: Targets as drivers of future progress or reflections of past action

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General Information

Summary

The academic paper “Targets as drivers of future progress or reflections of past action?” empirically measures which countries set ambitious targets, and whether ambition drives better decarbonization outcomes. We find that not only are countries setting targets they have already achieved, but, in some cases, those setting relatively unambitious targets actually perform better than others. In other words, it may be the path-dependence of past performance and other factors, such as policies and supporting institutions, and not targets, that signal continued or accelerated action. This issue is highly relevant for research and policy, as countries set and regularly update emissions targets but do not face enforcement mechanisms. This work is enabled by the provision of high-quality, granular and open-access policy data. This data is available on the [Climate Policy Atlas website](#) and can be easily visualized for non-expert users, providing an additional benefit to communicating with the broader public.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

The [Climate Policy Atlas](#) is a service provided by NFDI4Energy which provides high-quality, machine-readable data on climate and energy policies which can be visualized and downloaded for analysis. The underlying policy ontology and metadata are developed in [Task Area 4](#) and data are collected in [Task Area 2](#) . In [Task Area 6](#) use cases and show case are collected.

Deliverable (Showcase description)

Internal Documentation

Title: Targets as drivers of future progress or reflections of past action?

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Abstract: Strengthening climate action is essential to meeting the temperature targets of the Paris Agreement, and calls for stronger targets are growing increasingly urgent. However, questions remain about whether countries are setting ambitious targets and whether more ambitious targets lead to better performance. To address this, we conceptualize target ambition along two dimensions: whether targets were achieved at the time of setting, and whether they require additional effort. Then, we empirically assess our questions cross-nationally and across target domains using our dataset on renewable electricity, renewable energy, and climate (emissions-reduction) targets for all countries from 1997 to 2025. We find that high- and middle-income countries typically set ambitious targets, whereas low-income countries typically do not. However, in the long term, low-income countries also shift toward more ambitious targets. Targets do not consistently signal meaningful commitment. Sometimes ambitious targets are not associated with greater reliance on renewables or faster decarbonization, thereby raising doubts about their credibility, especially long-term climate (i.e., net-zero) targets. This also suggests that not only targets but also the path dependencies of past performance, policies, and supporting institutions can contribute to subsequent performance.

Link: The decarbonization target data are published online in the [Climate Policy Atlas](#).

NFDI4Energy input: NFDI4Energy Deliverable 2.2.2.2: Data on climate and renewable electricity targets (<https://zenodo.org/records/15476344>) & D4.5.1.1 Policy ontology (<https://zenodo.org/records/15583093>).

Energy research: We empirically analyze the relationship between decarbonization targets—covering renewable electricity, renewable energy, and climate (emissions reduction)—and performance, using complete time series datasets for 175, 140, and 186 countries, respectively. We focus on country-based, economy-wide targets from each country's first adoption year (1997 for climate, 2001 for renewable electricity, 2006 for renewable energy) until the most recent available year. We then explore the nature of targets and their support, and also test whether high ambition drives better outcomes and whether lower targets are more credible and likely to be met, comparing different determinants including income groups, democracy index, and carbon intensity. We find that targets are not significant predictors of subsequent performance, and that path dependence of better performance earlier rather predicts decarbonization.

Meta level: The main obstacle to empirical research on decarbonization and renewable electricity target effectiveness is the lack of machine-readable and comparable data points for cross-country analysis. For example, for renewable electricity targets, some countries announced targets as an additional increase instead of an absolute increase (i.e., 20 percentage points more than the current level). And for climate targets, they can be based on the base year, trajectory, business-as-usual, and intensity targets – they must therefore be normalized using 1990 as the base year for a consistent

dataset. Gathering and normalizing this target data must be done manually from different primary and secondary sources. Using the NFDI4Energy Target datasets enables us to perform robust cross-country analyses which would not have otherwise been possible.

Enhancement: The topic is of general interest, especially for policymakers. As a result, we have made the dataset accessible and reusable, and plan to make the research paper public on publication. We also presented this work in several conferences, including the Accelerating climate action: examining the role of the state in emission scenario workshop, the 46th International Association for Energy Economics (IAEE) International Conference, and the 2025 European Consortium for Political Research (ECPR) general conference.

Lessons learned: Since the beginning, we have been facing the main problems of socio-political dataset collection, which are the lack of interoperable energy policy ontology and the time and labor-intensive process of data collection. As a result, we not only manually collect the energy policy dataset but also develop an energy policy ontology, a data collection framework, and machine-readable metadata that can be reused for the next data update round, as shown in the [Climate Policy Atlas](#).

Brief sections for the website

The Showcase's Starting Point in Energy System Research

Countries around the world have set net-zero targets – but what do these mean, and how likely are they to be achieved? A research article by NFDI4Energy members uses open data to test the historic influence of climate and energy targets on policy outcomes. The analysis explores whether countries are setting targets that exceed their performance in the setting year and will require extra effort to meet, and which kinds of targets are associated with better performance in terms of emissions reductions and shares of renewable energy or electricity. The findings lend support to authors who question the role of targets in policy-making, as countries are not only setting targets they have already achieved, but, in some cases, those setting relatively unambitious targets actually perform better than others. In other words, it may be the path-dependence of past performance and other factors, such as policies and supporting institutions, and not targets, that signal continued or accelerated action.

Motivation and Research Requirements

There is a lack of open, machine-readable information on what targets countries have actually set and whether they are getting more ambitious over time which prevents assessments of their effectiveness. However, this is a highly relevant policy issue as the Paris Agreement encourages target-setting and ratcheting up ambition over time. There is therefore a need to provide data and analyses which are accessible to policymakers to inform decision-making.

NFDI4Energy Solution

The NFDI4Energy-funded [Climate Policy Atlas](#) provides open, machine-readable dataset for climate and renewable energy targets. We used this data to evaluate countries' climate performance, finding that target-setting behavior varies across country income groups, and that some countries set targets that they had already met in the year they set the targets. We have also created an online tool to visualize and explore renewable energy and climate targets to make the data more accessible to policy users.

(potential photo, if interested, from visualization website:)

